

Development of UAV-based LiDAR and multispectral measurement techniques for monitoring sediment intrusion in coastal wetlands

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ABSTRACT

This study presents an innovative measurement method utilizing Uncrewed Aerial Vehicle (UAV)-based Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) sensor and multispectral imaging to precisely monitor sand deposition in coastal wetlands. The classification scheme developed in this research distinguishes four key coastal land cover classes: **New Sand** (recently deposited sediments), **Old Sand** (previously deposited and partially stabilized sediments), **Vegetation** (coastal flora covering stabilized areas), and **Water** (including freshwater and brackish zones). These classes were identified based on spectral and elevation characteristics, enabling a high-resolution analysis of sediment transport and deposition processes. An initial classification using only LiDAR data achieved an accuracy of 83 %. By incorporating multispectral imaging and analysing the spectral signatures for each defined class (from multispectral measurements), we improved the classification accuracy to approximately 90 %. The spectral information from multispectral imaging proved crucial for differentiating sediment types, and refining the measurement process through better model tuning. Data aggregation was conducted using Google Earth Engine, enabling robust repetition of measurements, efficient handling of large datasets, and consistent data processing workflows. Our approach demonstrates significant advancements in measurement science by reducing time and costs associated with post-event environmental monitoring while improving data precision and accuracy. The combination of spectral data with LiDAR and leveraging spectral signatures for model tuning enhanced measurement outcomes by effectively propagating and minimizing uncertainties. The measurement framework developed offers a reliable and precise tool for tracking coastal sediment deposition, ensuring the reliability of results.

1. Introduction

Advancements in Uncrewed Aerial Vehicle (UAV) technology and specialized sensors have revolutionized measurement techniques in environmental monitoring, particularly in dynamic and complex coastal environments. High-resolution measurement methods are essential for precisely capturing geomorphological changes, however, they often generate large volumes of data that pose challenges in management, storage, and processing. Cloud computing platforms such as Google Earth Engine (GEE) have become crucial in addressing these challenges by enabling efficient handling of big data and facilitating advanced measurement data processing [1].

Coastal wetlands are sensitive interfaces between marine and terrestrial ecosystems, where accurate measurement of sediment

deposition is critical for understanding sediment dynamics, ecosystem health, and the impacts of extreme events such as storm surges [2]. Traditional measurement methods, including ground surveys and satellite imagery, often lack the spatial resolution or flexibility needed to capture fine-scale changes in these environments [3]. UAVs measurement systems equipped with Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) and multispectral sensors offer high-resolution spatial and spectral data, enhancing measurement accuracy and precision in this matter [4,5]. Despite these technological advancements, there remain significant challenges in measurement science related to:

- Processing Algorithms. Integrating data from multiple sensors necessitates advanced algorithms to effectively aggregate spatial and spectral information, maintaining measurement integrity [6]. The

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complexity of combining heterogeneous datasets requires processing techniques to ensure that measurement results are accurate and reliable.

- **Measurement Data Management.** It means, that handling large datasets generated by high-resolution sensors demands efficient data processing workflows that can preserve measurement quality while enabling scalability [7].

In addressing these challenges, this study aims to advance measurement methodologies by developing a robust framework that integrates UAV LiDAR and multispectral sensors for precise detection of sediment movement and deposition in coastal wetlands. The specific contributions to measurement science include:

- A designed measurement system that combines high-resolution spatial data from LiDAR with detailed spectral information from multispectral imaging, overcoming limitations of single-sensor approaches.
- Applied and tuned random forest model within the GEE platform was developed to process and classify the integrated datasets. By analysing spectral signatures for each measured wavelengths (in terms of using multispectral sensor and LiDAR Reflectance values), and characteristics of the terrain (elevation from Digital Terrain Model (DTM)), we improved measurement accuracy and reliability. Moreover, in [Supplementary Data](#) we present the **deep learning** classification methodology and results.
- Development of a novel algorithm (Fine2scale), which leverages an innovative integration of multiresolution and super pixel techniques to enhance sediment deposition detection.

1.1. Measurements in coastal research

Recent advancements in remote sensing measurements have revolutionized the approach to coastal science, offering insights into the morphology, structure, and evolution of coastal features. Techniques such as LiDAR, or multispectral imaging have become indispensable tools in the coastal management [8,9]. These methods enhance understanding and monitoring of current coastal processes. Moreover they facilitate the reconstruction of past landscapes and the prediction of future changes. For example, (Liu et al., 2023) used snow ice cover dataset based on satellite observation of passive microwave brightness temperatures to model multiyear behaviour of Antarctic Ice Sheet, which is crucial in estimating contribution of ice budget to global sea level changes [10], affecting coastal areas worldwide.[11] underlined rapid development of algorithms that aim to extract shorelines from measurement techniques and their temporal changes and compared selected approaches widely used in coastal science. There are also multiple examples of remote sensing applications to local or regional studies to enhance coastal assessment and understand coastal dynamics in particular geological settings (e.g. [12,13]).

Utilizing remotely acquired images and accurate digital elevation models processed on cloud computing platforms, we are able to see the advancement beyond traditional manual mapping methods. These earlier approaches were labour-intensive and lacked the consistency and detail required for global-scale analysis with local precision. The development of measurement frameworks based on high-resolution remote sensing data plays a crucial role in addressing these challenges by providing consistent, quantifiable metrics for monitoring changes in coastal environments [14]. Such precision and developed metrics are essential, as each coastal type presents specific challenges. For example, the delineation of sandy beaches from cliffs using satellite data provides critical insights for erosion and sediment transport studies (as volume) [3]. Measurement protocols help track how different geomorphic classes respond to climatic pressures and human activities, which is key for informing coastal management and conservation strategies. Moreover,

the understanding of coastal vulnerabilities and storm impacts has been significantly enhanced through remote sensing, where indicators derived from decades of satellite data allow for the assessment and ranking of coastal regions based on storm characteristics and vulnerabilities. This enables more effective planning and response strategies for natural disasters and climate change impacts [10]. By facilitating detailed, globally consistent analyses of coastal geomorphology, it enables—support a nuanced understanding and sustainable management of coastal environments. These advancements are not only academic but are also critical for enhancing the resilience and conservation of some of the planet’s most dynamic and vulnerable ecosystems [15].

1.2. Importance of sediment dynamics

Coastal zones are classified based on their morphological and geological characteristics, which influence sediment dynamics and overall environmental processes. The most common coastal types include sandy beaches, rocky coasts, estuaries, mangrove forests and coral reefs. Accurate classification of coastal environments is essential for understanding sediment movement and deposition, particularly in areas vulnerable to storm surges and extreme weather events. Coastal classifications typically focus on the physical characteristics of coastlines, which are shaped by processes such as wave action, tides, sediment accumulation, and erosion or biological activity [16,17]. This study specifically examines sandy depositional coasts, which are highly dynamic and experience frequent sediment shifts due to storms, waves, and tidal forces or aeolian activity. By categorizing coastlines based on sediment type and elevation changes, it becomes possible to track the evolution of vegetated coastal areas, beaches, and dune systems in response to coastal flooding—an essential factor in maintaining ecological stability and conserving habitats [18–20]. For these reasons, this article focuses on developing and applying a remote sensing-based measurement protocol for the rapid detection of sediment inputs in coastal environments, with a particular emphasis on coastal flooding sediments.

1.3. Coastal flooding sediments in the view of the measurements

Beside the devastating impact on the coast, flooding events tend to transport sediments from the offshore, beach and dune to back barrier environments [2,21]. Sedimentary records in the coastal zone are useful indicators of past climate and extreme flooding events. They are widely studied to complete regional palaeostorminess and palaeotsunami datasets, which is necessary for successful hazard assessment and disaster prevention policies [22,23]. Contemporary marine coastal flooding sediments are usually investigated shortly after the most notable catastrophes in post-event surveys. Fieldworks focuses on environmental impact of coastal flooding aim to record area of impact, devastation level of natural habitats, changes of shoreline position and sediment budget of the coast with further coastal recovery (e.g., [24–26]). Understanding coastal sediment dynamics is important, driven by the escalating impacts of climate change on coastal systems [19].

In coastal environments, sediment dynamics are driven by a combination of factors, including the hydrology, climate, and geomorphology of the region. The interference of these factors is particularly important in areas prone to marine coastal flooding, where sediments can be mobilized and deposited in new locations, altering the coastline [27]. The course of the storm impact on the coast depends on the storm surge regime [28]. If wave activity is limited to the beach or lower part of the dune (swash or collision regime), no sediment is moved by waves to the back-barrier environment. However, if marine water is overtopping the dune crest (overwash regime), then sediments are moved behind dunes and form landforms called washovers. Under high water levels notably exceeding dune crest height (inundation regime), waves transform the entire coast and move a large part of sediments to a back-barrier environment, forming wide, continuous or patchy sand

layers. Under overwash and inundation regimes, natural processes form easily detectable landforms and sediments [29]. If the distance to the site deposition is higher, the marine coastal flooding sediment trace may not be clear and its detection requires higher efforts [30]. Moreover, during storm events, sediment mobilization may be limited only to wind action when part of the dune deposits is moved to another coastal sub-environment (e.g., wetland, lagoon), and then it contributes to slight changes in local lithology, still being an archive of palaeostorminess [31].

Remote sensing measurements, have been used to monitor and analyse these changes, offering insights into both recent and historical sediment deposits [32]. In this study along the southern Baltic Sea, LiDAR and multispectral imagery were used to classify coastal flooding sediments formed by storms or infragravity waves. As long as the environment preserves traces of past events, these methods and protocols, particularly when integrated with machine learning algorithms, offer high classification accuracy. This enables a detailed study of sediment transport, erosion patterns, and deposition processes. By deriving the indicator from the classified imagery, we ensure consistent and quantifiable monitoring of coastal sediment dynamics, supporting more effective coastal management strategies. The view of the measurements methods are presented below in Table 1., together with our proposed method advances over already proposed methodologies in the literature.

1.4. Research Objectives

Based on the identified challenges and gaps in measurement science, this study aims to:

- 1) Create a measurement framework that integrates UAV-based LiDAR and multispectral imaging for precise detection and monitoring of sediment intrusion.
- 2) Implement advanced algorithms for data classification (including deep learning methods- please see [Supplementary Materials](#)) to improve measurement accuracy and efficiency, based on measurement spectra analysis.
- 3) Propose an innovative, multiresolution algorithm that fuses super-pixel segmentation with multi-scale Laplacian edge detection to accurately delineate sediment deposition patterns from high-resolution classification imagery.

2. Case study description

The classification and analysis of sediments formed by storm surges were performed at one selected location: the Mechelinki site, located in the Gulf of Gdańsk coastal area (Fig. 1), which is a part of the southern Baltic coastal zone, composed of sandy and diamictic cliffs, sandy barriers, and coastal peatlands. Seasonal storm events influence dynamic changes in beaches and shorelines, which are subjected to monitoring and forecasting studies (e.g., [40,41]). In this region, tsunamis are not expected, but coastal flooding deposits related to probable ‘meteotsunami’ and traces of other catastrophic events, not particularly related to storm surges, were recognized [38]. Moreover, coastal peatlands contain geological archives of past coastal flooding [37].

The area of interest, located close to Mechelinki village, has the status of Protected Nature Reserve, with limited anthropopressure [38,42]). Part of coastal wetland, which is oriented towards Puck Bay, separates the peatland from a narrow, sandy and sandy-gravelly beach (Fig. 1b). This beach is about 15–30 m wide and has an average slope of

Table 1
Comparison of Measurement Methods for Monitoring Sediment Intrusion in Coastal Wetlands.

Method	Measurement Technique	Spatial Resolution	Accuracy	Cost	Efficiency	Limitations	Reference
<i>Satellite Remote Sensing</i> (e.g., Landsat, Sentinel-2)	Optical Satellite Imagery	10–30 m	Moderate	Low	High (large areas)	Low spatial resolution; affected by cloud cover; limited temporal resolution	[33]; Liu, [5]; M. [34]
Advantages of Proposed Method Over This	Our method provides centimetre-level spatial resolution, unaffected by cloud cover, enabling precise measurements and detection of fine-scale changes.						
<i>UAV Photogrammetry (RGB Cameras)</i>	UAV-based Photogrammetry (SfM)	High (2–5 cm)	Moderate to High	Moderate	High	Less accurate elevation data in vegetated areas; relies on good lighting conditions	[4–6,13,35]
Advantages of Proposed Method Over This	Our method integrates LiDAR, providing accurate elevation data even in vegetated areas, and improves measurement precision, additional use of multispectral camera enhance the spectral differences between vegetation and recorded sediments.						
<i>Airborne LiDAR (Manned Aircraft)</i>	Airborne Laser Scanning	Moderate (0.5–1 m)	High	Very High	Moderate	High operational costs; less flexible scheduling; lower spatial resolution compared to UAV LiDAR	[36]
Advantages of Proposed Method Over This	Our UAV-based LiDAR offers higher spatial resolution (up to 10 cm), lower operational costs, and greater flexibility in data collection scheduling. Also the footprint from Airborne LiDAR is larger compared the UAV-LiDAR.						
<i>Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR)</i>	Subsurface Radar Scanning	High (sub-meter)	High (subsurface)	High	Low	Limited to subsurface data; slow data collection; not suitable for large-area surface monitoring	[30,37,38]
Advantages of Proposed Method Over This	Our method efficiently covers large areas, capturing high-resolution surface data essential for monitoring sediment intrusion and geomorphological changes. However, GPR can show what is below the surface.						
<i>Terrestrial Laser Scanning (TLS)</i>	Terrestrial Laser Scanning	Very High (mm-level)	Very High	High	Low	Limited coverage area; time-consuming; requires multiple setups; line-of-sight limitations	[9,39]
Advantages of Proposed Method Over This	Our UAV-based LiDAR overcomes line-of-sight limitations, covers larger areas quickly, and reduces the need for multiple setups, enhancing efficiency. Additionally, using LiDAR alone achieves lower accuracy compared to a combined approach.						
<i>Field Sampling and Laboratory Analysis</i>	Physical Sample Collection and Analysis	Point data	Very High (at points)	Moderate to High	Very Low	Time-consuming; labour-intensive; limited spatial coverage; delays between data collection and results	[29,30,37]
Advantages of Proposed Method Over This	Our method provides immediate, high-resolution spatial data over large areas, reducing time and labour while increasing measurement efficiency. However, to validate the measurement protocol it is recommended to collect Field Sampling for testing.						

Fig. 1. The location of the study site. A – Gulf of Gdańsk located in the southern part of the Baltic Sea. B – Mechelinki study site marked with a semi-transparent blue net. Arrows indicate examples of analyzed sub-environments that define classes (compare different surfaces in Fig. 3). (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

5.7°, with the steepest incline reaching up to 10°. Dune ridges are either non-existent or poorly formed, with an average relative height of around 0.5 m and an absolute height of 1.9 m above sea level. The dominant sediment is medium sand with admixture of coarse sand and gravel clasts. Coarser sediment accumulates in the swash zone and is moved occasionally to the middle and upper part of the beach. Marine coastal flooding sediments are composed mainly of medium and coarse sand, delivered from other coastal subenvironments. They are sorted during the transport according to grain sizes and densities [38,42]. Stronger storms (one event per several years) create depositional landforms (washovers), which are up to 20 cm thick and reach the landward distance of about 10–90 m from the dune crest. The average area of individual washovers is 630 m² [29].

This site provides an opportunity to examine the results of developed measurement protocol and compare its impact of storm surges on coastal morphology and its depositional record under various storm surge regimes [28]. By employing spatial data derived from UAV-based LiDAR and multispectral imagery, the research detects surface sediment distribution. It offers valuable insights into the sedimentary processes driving coastal sediment migration and their long-term impact on vegetated wetlands.

3. Materials and methods

To reach the study aims, a comprehensive research workflow (Fig. 2) began with UAV surveys capturing high-resolution multispectral imagery and LiDAR data over coastal areas. Four distinct classes were identified through visual inspection (Fig. 3). These classes were examined for their spectral reflectance characteristics across both reflected (multispectral) and emitted (laser scanning) wavelengths. The computing was performed using Google Earth Engine. The evaluated outcome model was analysed from measurement protocol and improved using Principal Component Analysis (PCA), feature importance analysis, and by including derivative characteristics like: Normalized Difference Index (NDI) (calculated using the two most important spectral features from the multispectral camera), slope and aspect. Then, the model was evaluated with a confusion matrix and accuracy assessment statistics.

3.1. Measurement techniques

3.1.1. Multispectral data processing

In this study, we employed the PIX4Dmapper software to conduct an UAV-based photogrammetric data processing. The data, collected by the Micasense Dual Band camera system, encompassing an array of spectral

Research Workflow

Fig. 2. The research workflow.

bands including 10 spectral bands was captured with the DJI Matrice 300 Real-Time Kinematic (RTK) drone. The acquisition covered an area of 0.039 km², and the project achieved an average Ground Sampling Distance (GSD) of 5 cm. The dataset comprised 3187 out of 3250 images per band successfully calibrated, marking a 98 % calibration rate, with each image containing a median of 6330 keypoints. The number of calibrated images resulted from the fact that after turning on the camera, we waited for flight clearance while images were continuously taken, and that in one dataset, we recorded images dedicated to radiometric calibration on a reference plate with specified reflectance values. The camera optimization phase revealed a mere 0.49 % relative difference between initial and optimized internal camera parameters. Georeferencing was performed using five Ground Control Points (GCPs), measured as XYZ coordinates via Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) surveying (EPSG:2177) in RTK mode. The objective was to generate an orthophotomosaic for each spectral band separately (Coastal Blue – 444 nm, Blue – 475 nm, Green1 – 531 nm, Green2 – 560 nm, Red1- 650 nm, Red2 – 668 nm, RedEdge1 – 705 nm, RedEdge2 – 717 nm, RedEdge3 – 740 nm, NIR – 840 nm). To achieve this, we utilized Pix4D software (manufacturer: Pix4D S.A. Switzerland), where the same five GCPs were manually indicated for each band. After image alignment and orthophotomosaic generation, we assessed the positional differences between the GNSS-measured GCPs and their corresponding locations in the orthophotomosaics. The root mean square (RMS) error of 0.05 m was calculated from these discrepancies. The orthomosaics were generated with a resolution of 5 cm/pixel.

3.1.2. LiDAR data processing

Within the workflow of processing LiDAR data captured by the UAV (DJI Matrice 300 RTK)-mounted AlphaAir450 (Manufacturer: CHCNAV, China) laser scanning system, we used the Copre software (Manufacturer: CHCNAV, China), extending its utility beyond point cloud extraction to include trajectory alignment. This crucial step ensures the high precision of geospatial data by correcting any positional inaccuracies in the UAV's flight path, leveraging the system's onboard GNSS and IMU (Inertial Measurement Unit) data together with ASG EUPOS [43] reference station. The next steps after point cloud extraction were performed in R language [44]. Following the obtained point cloud, the software was used to perform the task of filtering and classifying the results distinguishing ground points from non-ground elements such as vegetation and structures (Cloth Simulation Function [45]). This refined classification was essential for generating an accurate Digital Terrain Model (DTM). The software employs interpolation algorithms to transform the classified ground points into a seamless, continuous surface representation of the terrain, devoid of above-ground features. Because the study site is characterized by a small area, the kriging method was used for that purpose. The resultant DTM was a high-resolution and georeferenced model. Lastly, all of the data was saved as GeoTIFF surface rasters (32-bit, floating point samples).

3.2. Cloud computing in Google Earth Engine

Once collected and stored on a hard-drive with delivered and created

Class name	Description	Sample Ortho image	Sample NIR image	Histograms of NIR
New sand	Beach, aeolian or washover sand deposited in the past year, covering old vegetation or barely covered by new vegetation			
Old sand	Washover and aeolian sand deposited in the past, redistributed, deformed, partially or fully covered by low vegetation			
Vegetation	Plants that fully cover the ground surface built with sand, mud or peat			
Water	Fresh water in canals or marine brackish water in the swash zone			

Fig. 3. Classified objects – types of surfaces related to analysed coastal sub-environments.

software, the separate.tiff images for each band with different characteristics data were imported into GEE, where they were formatted for seamless integration as composites. In this way, acquired multispectral datasets were merged into a single composite image, augmented by processed LiDAR data that extracted elevation and surface characteristics, thereby enriching the analytical foundation with additional depth and detail. Radiometric indices, derived from the multispectral data, further enhanced distinguishing between various coastal features.

Over 3100 Ground Truth Points (GTPs) were manually identified for identifiable coastal features such as New Sand, Old Sand, Vegetation, and Water, extracted from the UAV data, and which formed the basis for a robust training and validation dataset for the proposed methodology (we used a common ratio 70 % GTPs for training and randomly chosen 30 % GTPs for validation). Then, the Random Forest classifier [46] within the GEE was trained on the created composite, equipping the system for the automated classification of the coastal environment. This methodology was selected due to many successful applications in classifying environmental data and land use land cover (e.g., [1,47,48] and for the possibility of cloud computing, which enhanced performance of high-resolution datasets processing and allowed us for free will choose of specific algorithms we would like to apply. However, we noticed the need of development new methodologies, that's why we also present the classification through deep-learning, which we put in [Supplementary Materials](#).

The trained classifier subsequently categorized the landscape into distinct features, visualized within GEE with a unique colour palette for each class. It was applied to the composite dataset, and the resulting classifications were assessed using the validation GTPs. A confusion matrix was generated to evaluate the classifier's performance, providing insights into the accuracy and reliability of the classification results.

To quantitatively assess the impact of varying the number of trees on classifier performance, we implemented an iterative analysis using a function that cycles through a range of candidate tree counts. We defined this sequence using `ee.List.sequence(start, end, step)` with `start = 10`, `end = 150`, and a step of 10. For each candidate value (e.g., 10, 20, 30, ..., 150), we trained a new Random Forest classifier with `ee.Classifier.smileRandomForest(numTrees)`, using a fixed training dataset composed of features extracted from our composite image along with

their corresponding class labels. Each trained classifier was then applied to a validation dataset, and we computed a confusion matrix to derive its overall accuracy. These accuracy values were stored in an array, and we visualized the relationship between the number of trees and accuracy using `ui.Chart.array.values()`.

As a different approach, enhancing the relevance of our study we are proposing the deep learning classification methodology, which can be found in [Supplementary Materials](#). In this approach, we are proposing a Multi-Layer Perceptron (MLP) [49], a type of artificial neural network well-suited for structured data where spatial relationships are not the primary feature of interest. Unlike Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) [50], which excel in spatial pattern recognition, MLPs are more appropriate for problems where data is structured as tabular features rather than images with strong spatial dependencies.

3.2.1. Feature and model evaluation, hypertuning

To analyse feature importance, we utilized `the.explain()` function within GEE on the trained classifier. This function provided detailed insights into the classifier's internal workings, including the relative importance of each feature used in the classification. The resulting information was stored in a dictionary. To visualize the feature importance, we converted this dictionary into a Feature Collection, enabling us to leverage GEE's charting capabilities to create a visual representation of feature importance. This analysis helped in identifying which inputs were most influential in predicting the sediment deposits, directly addressing the research gap regarding the relevance of different types of data and analyses. Moreover, the workflow further explored the spectral signatures of the classified features, providing insights into the distinct reflectance properties of each class. This step was geared towards understanding the underlying reasons for the model's classification decisions and refining the classification approach based on spectral characteristics.

Hyperparameter tuning in Random Forest classification optimized model performance by adjusting key parameters. PCA identified the most influential variables, while geospatial features from LiDAR-based DTM and a NDI improved model accuracy. In this regard, slope (steepness) was computed using `ee.Terrain.slope()`. Aspect (slope orientation) was derived with `ee.Terrain.aspect()` function, aiding in landform

exposure analysis. NDI, calculated via *normalizedDifference()*, used the Green (531 nm) and Red Edge (740 nm) bands, selected based on feature importance analysis. The validation dataset was used for assessment of each tree count. The accuracy was determined by comparing the prediction against the actual ground truth points using a confusion matrix (*errorMatrix.accuracy()* function). The accuracy metrics from each iteration were collected into a list. This collection allowed for a comparative analysis to identify the number of trees that yielded the highest accuracy [51].

3.3. Fine2scale algorithm development

Our Fine2Scale algorithm integrates multiresolution edge analysis with SLIC superpixel segmentation to enhance the detection of sediment deposition patterns, with complete code provided in the [Supplementary Materials](#). The workflow begins by resampling and preprocessing high-resolution classified imagery— Although our data were collected at 5 cm GSD, we resampled them to 10 cm. This resampling step reflects the approximately 5 cm RMS alignment error derived from our GCPs; thus, maintaining a 10 cm resolution avoids artificially inflating spatial precision and reduces the risk of misclassifying minor geometric discrepancies as sediment features. Moreover, we also generated a 1 m resolution classification image, recognizing 1 m as a common resolution in publicly available spatial repositories (e.g., LiDAR-derived raster products). This side-by-side evaluation highlights how fine-scale patterns of sand deposit (10 cm) may be generalized or “smoothed out” at coarser resolutions, influencing the perceived extent and continuity of older, storm-deposited sands now partially vegetated yet still identifiable via their spectral signatures and subtle topographic cues.

The Fine2Scale pipeline proceeds in several key steps. First, the image is converted to grayscale and enhanced using Contrast Limited Adaptive Histogram Equalization (CLAHE). Gaussian blurring at multiple sigma values then generates a multi-scale Laplacian edge map, capturing both coarse and fine textural details. In parallel, SLIC superpixel segmentation [52] partitions the image into spatially coherent regions, thus extracting boundaries that complement gradient-based edges. These two edge maps—Laplacian-based and superpixel-based—are fused nonlinearly using a sigmoid function, accentuating consistently detected features while suppressing noise. As an additional measure, Canny edge detection [53], is performed to isolate smaller, dot-like features that might otherwise be overlooked. The combined edge map is then refined using morphological opening to remove isolated noise, followed by skeletonization to produce a one-pixel-wide boundary. Finally, the algorithm extracts contours from this refined map and overlays them on the original image in a single, uniform colour, creating a visually clear and computationally robust delineation of potential sediment deposits. To further demonstrate the algorithm’s relevance to coastal geomorphology, we apply a series of binary thresholding and Canny filtering steps to classify the fused output into “sand” and “non-sand” zones. Pixels identified as Old Sand are grouped under “past sediments,” whereas vegetation and water constitute the non-sand category. By mapping these boundaries and measuring consistency across adjacent pixels, Fine2Scale helps confirm whether observed sandy patches are part of older overwash deposits or nascent accumulations masked by vegetation. Such fine-scale insights guide potential in situ geophysical surveys (e.g., Ground Penetrating Radar) and enrich reconstructions of local coastal history, where partially vegetated sand layers can persist as residual signatures of storm activity.

4. Results

Classification outcomes at the Mechelinki site were based on assigned points per class used for classification, with 1178 features for the Old Sand, 1131 for the New Sand, 669 for the Vegetation and 138 for the Water classes. We further explored the measurement results (change in classification accuracy from 83 % to 90 % based on the spatial data

input) and spectral significance of each identified point in training and validation, therefore analysing their sensitivity in the classification process. This step-by-step examination, visually supported at first by Fig. 4 – showcasing multispectral results (each processed band in reflectance grayscale), DTM (in meters grayscale), and the 1st Principal Component – lays the groundwork for a comprehensive discussion and conclusion of our research findings.

The software processing outcomes revealed that the angular separation, measured in arcminutes, generally remains close to zero, with notable deviations at the beginning and end of the measurement flight (Fig. 5b). These results were obtained as a result of static and dynamic calibration. The estimated Position Standard Deviation was below 1 cm, a result achieved by aligning the trajectory to the reference base station. The number of calibrated images was 96 %. The chart depicting the calibrated multispectral images shows that uncalibrated images, marked in red, were recorded during the drone’s ascent to cruising altitude (Fig. 5c). The coverage of images was smallest at the boundary (Fig. 5d). The images were processed each per band.

Within the analytical framework, we leveraged a Random Forest classifier on the GEE platform to discern the relative significance of various features in enhancing the model’s predictive capability. Utilizing the classifier’s *explain()* function, we extracted a detailed account of feature importance values, each corresponding to a specific model variable and its inferred importance score (Fig. 6).

In the case of using only multispectral cameras in the classification (Fig. 6a), a significant impact of the Coastal Blue (444 nm) and Red Edge (717 nm) channels was observed. High, yet slightly lesser significance was observed in the channels Red Edge (740 nm), NIR (840 nm), Green (560 nm), Red (650 nm), and Green (531 nm), while lesser importance was assigned to the Red (668 nm) and Blue (475 nm) channels, with the least importance given to Red Edge (705 nm). When using only the LiDAR sensor (Fig. 6b), the most significant factors were observed in the DTM and the reflectance of the recorded points, with lesser importance given to the calculated elements of Slope and Aspect. When combining multispectral and LiDAR sensor datasets (Fig. 6c), the digital elevation model was found to be most significant. However, it should be noted that the classification accuracy from the confusion matrix for using LiDAR sensor alone was 83 %, while for multispectral cameras alone it was 86 %, and their combination achieved 87.5 % in accuracy. The best results were obtained using data from multispectral cameras, LiDAR, and their calculated elements: normalized difference index, slope, aspect, PCA scores (Fig. 6d). The accuracy given with the confusion matrix was up to 90 %. Moreover, as illustrated in Fig. 7, we conducted an evaluation to identify the optimal hyperparameters on the validation dataset that would yield the most accurate classification results. A function named *tuneNumberOfTrees* was employed and systematically varied the number of trees in the Random Forest classifier to determine the configuration that maximized classification accuracy. Presented accuracies were plotted against the number of trees using *ui.Chart.array.values()*. The best accuracy was achieved at the 150 number of trees (Fig. 7). However, beyond a threshold of 60–80 trees, the accuracy of the model did not exhibit substantial improvement.

The classification results of the Mechelinki site showed good agreement with environmental components (Fig. 8). In general, new sand class corresponded to beach, washover and deflation sand accumulated during the past storm season. It entered the old sand class when topographic conditions favoured the movement of the sediment, mainly through erosional corridors (Fig. 8). Old sand class delineated from the landward part of the vegetated area. Partially, it was correlated with lobate shapes derived from the digital terrain model. However, in many cases, actual traces of washovers exceeded the landward limit of the old sand class, extending as scattered patterns within peatland (Fig. 8). Vegetation class accurately corresponded to peat environment, high grass, bushes and low grass, which covered older washovers and formed small hillocks within dune ridges. The most misclassifications in point class allocation were observed in water regions. For the swash zone of

Fig. 4. The results of imagery measurements, presenting the following bands: A – Coastal Blue, B – Blue, C – Green1, D – Green2, E- 650 Red1, F – Red2, G – Red Edge1, H – Red Edge2, I Red Edge3, NIR – 840 nm, K – DTM (Digital Terrain Model), L – 1st PC (Principal Component).

the beach area, the main boundary separating fresh sand from older deposits was readily discernible (Fig. 8).

In our study, the sediment deposition within coastal vegetation areas was evaluated using multiple methods, each providing distinct insights into the spatial dynamics of sand intrusion. The classification results (Fig. 9 Panel A) offer a high-resolution baseline where fine-scale

differences between vegetation and sediment are evident. When this data is resampled to a coarser 1 m resolution, the interpolation method influences the outcome. Bilinear (Fig. 9 Panel B) and bicubic (Fig. 9 Panel C) interpolations produce smoother transitions, blending subtle features that are visible at finer scales, while the k-nearest neighbours approach (Fig. 9 Panel D) preserves discrete boundaries at the cost of

Fig. 5. Software processing results including image processing, and trajectory results. A – The Mechelinki study site, delineated by the spatial extents of LiDAR and multispectral data acquisition. B – Details pertaining to trajectory alignment. C – A chart representing the calibrated multispectral images. D – Spatial density of overlapping images.

introducing a more blocky appearance. These resampling techniques highlight the inherent trade-off between resolution and the clarity of small-scale features in the data. Moreover, when applying a polygon delineation algorithm directly to the high-resolution data (Fig. 9 Panel E), the resulting maps capture a complex network of fine boundaries and nested features that are crucial for accurately delineating sediment deposition. In contrast, applying the same algorithm to the resampled 1 m data (Fig. 9 Panel F) results in a significant loss of detail, as many of the intricate boundaries merge into larger, more generalized zones. Overall, while the 10 cm data provides the detailed granularity necessary for precise measurement of sediment deposition, the 1 m resampled products—depending on the interpolation method—offer a broader overview that may be suitable for regional assessments but can obscure critical micro-scale sediment dynamics.

5. Discussion

5.1. Measurements

The study encompasses UAV-based laser scanning and multispectral imaging to acquire detailed topographical and spectral data across the targeted coastal area. The position of the trajectory, with an estimated standard deviation of around 1 cm, highlights the precision in capturing the scanner’s movement throughout the data acquisition process and

indicates its correct processing. This level of accuracy was essential for creating highly detailed and accurate point clouds and then topographical models. The streamlined data processing workflow, augmented by meticulous capture metrics, highlights the successful application of these technologies for precise coastal mapping. However, the accuracy of such datasets hinges critically on correct alignment and georeferencing, necessitating the use of GNSS reference stations and GCPs [54]. Although post-acquisition data integration is feasible, direct georeferencing during data capture is preferable for ensuring the reproducibility of results. In scenarios where access to online GNSS reference station databases is unavailable, alternatives like DJI’s proprietary reference station offer viable solutions, simplifying the geodetic setup required for precise data acquisition. Furthermore, the integrity of satellite systems network assessments can be gauged using specific indicators such as the vertical dilution of precision (VDOP), horizontal dilution of precision (HDOP), and positional dilution of precision (PDOP) [55,56]. In our study, VDOP values below 1 and HDOP values under 1.5 indicate robust vertical and horizontal positioning capabilities, respectively, while a PDOP of around 1.5 reflected commendable overall positioning accuracy, encompassing both vertical and horizontal measurements.

When processing multispectral imaging data, the role of GCPs becomes crucial [57]. Our results of georeferencing (an RMS error of approximately 5 cm) attest to the feasibility of processing multispectral

Fig. 6. Feature Importance and Accuracy Assessment. A – case of using only multispectral camera, B – case of using only LiDAR, C – case of combining multispectral camera and LiDAR, D – case of combining multispectral camera and LiDAR with addition of derivatives. 444–840 corresponds to channels of the multispectral camera, ‘m asl’ is the elevation above mean sea level, r is reflectance, sl is the slope, ar is an aspect, NDI is normalized difference index, and PC1-3 are consecutive Principal Components explaining most part of the dataset variance.

data based on their georeferenced metrics alone. Yet, it is crucial to conduct distinct georeferencing for GCPs across each spectral band to avoid misalignments [58]. Failure to do so could result in spatial discrepancies in the final mosaic, potentially impacting the delineation and accuracy of classified features [59]. Despite the success in enhancing measurement accuracy and providing detailed environmental

assessments, several limitations and challenges were encountered that warrant discussion. Addressing these issues is crucial for refining the methodologies and improving the reliability of future measurements in similar environmental monitoring efforts.

One of the primary challenges identified was ensuring the calibration and stability of the sensors used. Instrumental uncertainties due to

Fig. 7. Hypertuning for training dataset showing increasing validation accuracy with a growing number of trees and stabilization of the accuracy for the number of trees greater than 60–80.

Fig. 8. A – Orthophotomap for the Mechelinki study site. B – Hillshade visualization. C – The classification results. Numbers correspond to examples of 1 – fresh beach sand, 2 – erosional corridors facilitating sand transport, 3 – sand accumulated during the winter season (mainly of aeolian origin), 4 – reworked and partially covered washover sand accumulated in previous seasons, 5 – wetland vegetation, 6 – water in the freshwater canal, 7 – brackish water in the swash zone.

sensor drift and calibration errors can substantially impact measurement accuracy. Regular calibration using certified reference materials is essential to maintain sensor performance levels. The accuracy of the UAV’s positioning system emerged as another critical factor influencing measurement precision. Although the UAV’s GPS/IMU system provided a positioning standard deviation of approximately 1 cm, positioning errors due to satellite signal multipath effects and atmospheric disturbances were still present. To enhance positioning accuracy, the utilization of advanced GNSS technologies, such as RTK system, is recommended. Moreover, for the LiDAR sensor, both static and dynamic alignments must be performed before and after each mission to preserve

IMU accuracy and minimize drift errors in positioning [60].

The accuracy of georeferencing is highly sensitive to both the number and spatial arrangement of GCPs [61]. Insufficient or poorly distributed GCPs commonly introduce systematic errors, especially in regions located far from GCP clusters. Although increasing the number of GCPs generally improves georeferencing outcomes, the spatial distribution of these points is equally critical. A dense but poorly distributed network might still leave certain areas inadequately controlled, undercutting the benefits of increased GCP density. For instance, [62] discuss how varying GCP layouts—from minimal configurations (5–6 points) to denser networks—can influence the root-mean-square error

Fig. 9. Comparison of sediment deposition detection in coastal vegetation areas. Panel A shows the high-resolution classification results (10 cm), while Panels B, C, and D display 1 m resampling using bilinear, bicubic, and k-NN methods. Panels E and F illustrate polygon delineation applied to the 10 cm and Fine2Scale algorithm to 1 m data.

(RMSE) of final models. They highlight the importance of placing GCPs around the perimeter as well as within the interior of the survey area to mitigate extrapolation errors. Similarly, [63] underscore the need to maintain adequate spacing between GCPs (e.g., placing them at consistent intervals of tens to hundreds of meters, depending on project scale) to detect and correct for radial errors in larger mapping projects.

Moreover, certain habitat types or terrain conditions (e.g., dense vegetation vs. open ground) can necessitate an adjusted GCP strategy to preserve line-of-sight to both the sensors and satellite signals [64]. Researchers often recommend tailoring GCP density to site complexity—for example, more GCPs in heterogeneous or topographically variable landscapes [62]. Consequently, to achieve centimetre-level precision, a typical guideline is to use at least 5–10 well-distributed GCPs for smaller sites, spacing them so that no large portions of the area remain distant from any control point [63]. This approach helps counter systematic distortions and ensures that every portion of the scene is within a reasonable radius of a GCP.

In our study, direct georeferencing methods using RTK provided an advantage by improving the initial aerotriangulation, as the middle positions of our images were known to within a few centimetres [65]. This reduced our reliance on a large number of GCPs, allowing us to conclude that 5–10 GCPs were adequate, as long as they were distributed to cover different sections and habitat types thoroughly. A key stipulation is that GCPs must not cluster in one line or proximity. Where terrain features or varied land cover might compromise line-of-sight or uniform distribution, additional points may be warranted to reinforce local accuracy.

The implications of poor GCP placement can be particularly severe in multispectral imaging. Each spectral band is captured with slightly different lens parameters and sensor orientations, so misalignments in georeferencing can propagate errors across the final mosaic, jeopardizing subsequent classification or change-detection analyses. For this reason, it is often recommended to perform independent or carefully verified georeferencing for each band [61]. With proper GCP spacing—tailored to each habitat type—and adherence to best practices in direct georeferencing, the alignment between spectral bands can be maintained at the centimetre level, enhancing overall mapping accuracy and reliability.

Data processing posed significant challenges due to the large volume and high resolution of the datasets. The initial processing time, which exceeded 15 h, indicates the need for efficient data processing workflows. Developing or adopting more robust data processing algorithms can optimize processing time and improve keypoint matching. Enhanced feature detection algorithms are also necessary to increase the number of matched keypoints, particularly in areas with low texture or distinctive features. Improved algorithms can detect more reliable features, resulting in better alignment and reduced uncertainties in measurements.

Although we integrated multispectral data and assembled a notably large training dataset, a residual error rate of about 10 % still emerged. On closer examination of the confusion matrix and site-specific errors, we discovered that misclassifications were most prevalent in areas of deep shadow adjacent to dense vegetation canopies. Spectral signatures in these shadowed regions tended to mimic those of darker surfaces (e.g., water or shaded sediment), thereby confusing the model despite the abundance of training points. While expanding the training dataset generally helps, in this case simply “throwing more data” at the problem was not the limiting factor; we already had robust coverage of most classes. Instead, the key to improving accuracy lies in better handling the subtle spectral overlap introduced by shadows. In future work, we plan to implement additional preprocessing steps (e.g., shadow detection and compensation algorithms) or more advanced classification techniques (e.g., convolutional neural networks with built-in strategies for complex illumination effects). These enhancements can directly target the root cause of misclassification—rather than merely increasing the size of an already large training set—thereby further reducing model

uncertainty and elevating overall accuracy.

Radiometric calibration using reflectance targets may introduce uncertainties if the targets are not properly characterized or if lighting conditions change. Ensuring that calibration targets are clean, properly placed, and measured under similar lighting conditions is crucial (before and after the flight mission). Standardizing reflectance calibration procedures can improve the consistency and accuracy of reflectance measurements across different datasets and acquisition times.

In conclusion, while the integration of UAV-based LiDAR scanning and multispectral imaging has demonstrated significant potential for high-precision environmental measurements, addressing the identified limitations is essential for improving measurement accuracy and reliability. Implementing the recommended enhancements, such as advanced sensor calibration, utilization of high-precision positioning systems, optimized data acquisition strategies, and improved data processing algorithms, will contribute to the advancement of measurement methodologies. These improvements are crucial for providing more precise data to inform coastal management and conservation strategies, ultimately supporting the sustainable management of coastal ecosystems.

5.2. GEE Employ

The implementation of a comprehensive environmental analysis within the GEE framework was a critical component of our study, aimed at enhancing the processing of coastal datasets. A key step in our methodology was the manual generation of GTPs from distinct land cover classes, such as New Sand, Old Sand, Vegetation, and Water. These GTPs were instrumental in training the classification model and enabled the accurate identification of these features within the coastal landscape [66]. One of the very important issues which we covered during the analysis was the cloud computing and time-saving processes that we undertook. Moreover we generated images to tune the classification as slope, aspect, normalized index, including in the GEE code, but of which in time of manually performing such a processing could be time-consuming [7]; [67].

The workflow encourages interdisciplinary research engagement by leveraging GEE’s platform to refine methodologies and different applications of remote sensing to the coastal environment, which, due to its dynamic nature, is difficult to study. For example, [68] focused on developing algorithms for shoreline extraction using satellite data and GEE but [69] argued that finding a global solution for environmental topics, sometimes may be too challenging to be effective on a global scale. However, the consideration of environmental dynamics may bring satisfactory and useful tools employed in GEE [11]. Moreover, localized, high-resolution data integration (provided by, e.g. UAV-based LiDAR and multispectral imaging) is much less explored but may bring the data useful for understanding particular coastal settings and environmental issues. For example, [34] focused on vegetation classification accuracy, using satellite data and GEE’s machine learning capabilities, but did not integrate multispectral and DTM data. The above examples show that recent studies deliver state-of-the-art solutions based on satellite-derived data but also underscore the workflow’s potential to transform our understanding and management of coastal environments through the integration of local and regional UAV-derived data within Google Earth Engine. This process is critical for optimizing the model’s performance and ensuring the highest possible accuracy in classifying coastal landscape features and analysing coastal data at different scales.

[70] emphasized deforestation detection accuracy using GEE and satellite data, but the study could have also achieved a detailed feature importance analysis, which could emphasize critical features for the study, reduce noise, and improve the efficiency and accuracy of subsequent analyses and visualizations [71]. This approach enriches the research methodology and provides deep insights into the environmental dynamics at play, supporting more informed decision-making and conservation efforts [3,72,73]. Through the precise classification

of coastal features, the assessment of model accuracy, and the examination of feature importance in GEE based on differently acquired datasets, the proposed workflow lays the groundwork for future research aiming at improving research methodology, understanding and management of coastal environments.

In the context of data fusion within GEE, it is crucial to note that

compositing multiple datasets harnesses each sensor’s unique spectral, spatial, or temporal advantages. GEE’s integrated preprocessing routines—including atmospheric correction and cloud masking—ensure that fused images remain internally consistent and accurately represent ground conditions [67], but they are only based for satellite imagery. In our case, we rely on the proper distribution and alignment of GCPs, as

Fig. 10. Mean spectral signatures and error estimates for the four land cover classes. Panel A: mean spectra signatures. Panels B, C, D, and E: corresponding spectral signatures for New Sand, Old Sand, Vegetation, and Water, respectively, with error bars indicating the difference between mean values and lower bounds.

even minor misalignment can severely degrade the quality of feature fusion. GEE circumvents these issues by automatically standardizing coordinate reference systems, thereby aligning all layers on a common grid.

Furthermore, GEE's robust capacity for time-series analysis aids investigations into dynamic phenomena, such as sediment deposition or vegetation cycles. By creating composite images linked to specific timestamps, researchers gain deeper insights into processes that evolve over days, months, or years. Near-instant feedback in the GEE environment also accelerates methodological refinements—whether through exploratory normalization strategies, custom band math, or different scaling approaches—without imposing heavy local computing demands. The platform's extensive historical archives similarly enable retrospective analyses of coastal erosion, urban sprawl, and other changing land surface characteristics, broadening spatiotemporal perspectives.

Nonetheless, recognizing that certain limitations of conventional fusion approaches persist, we devised a deep learning-based methodology in tandem with the **Fine2Scale** algorithm (all necessary additional information we provided in the [Supplementary Data](#)). By synthesizing superpixel segmentation and multiresolution edge detection, Fine2Scale provides high-resolution identification of sediment deposits and other subtle surface features. In this manner, we integrate the strengths of GEE's scalable data handling with advanced machine learning frameworks, offering a more comprehensive and adaptive solution for modern geospatial challenges.

5.3. Improving the classification

Our classification approach employed a Random Forest classifier trained on the manually prepared training dataset. This machine learning model was chosen for its effectiveness in handling complex environmental high-resolution datasets, capable of discerning subtle differences between various land cover types. The classification results, visualized through an appropriate colour scheme, revealed the distribution of New Sand, Old Sand, Vegetation, and Water, offering a clear and detailed view of the coastal environment's current state. Random Forest stood out for its predictive accuracy, achieved by averaging the outcomes of multiple decision trees to mitigate overfitting – a common challenge in environmental modelling [36]. Another key advantage was its feature importance capability, which identified the most significant variables affecting the model's predictions, guiding effective conservation and management decisions.

The accuracy assessment of the classification process, conducted through a comparison of the classified image against the validation GTP dataset, yielded a confusion matrix and an accuracy metric. These results provided a quantitative measure of our model's performance, underscoring the reliability of our classification outcomes. Furthermore, the feature importance analysis, facilitated by the classifier's explain function, unveiled the relative significance of different bands and indices in the classification process. A comparison of the spectral signatures for each class, as visualized in [Fig. 10](#), further illuminates the distinct optical properties of the various land cover types. For example, the New Sand signature—depicted by a yellow line—exhibits a clear peak around the 840 nm band, indicating a higher reflectance that likely corresponds to freshly deposited, granular sediments. In contrast, its reflectance dips near the 475 nm and NDI bands, suggesting these wavelengths are less sensitive to the surface properties of new sand. Although the Old Sand signature follows a similar overall trend, noticeable differences in reflectance values hint at alterations in sediment composition and maturity over time. The Vegetation signature, shown by a green line, diverges markedly from the sand signatures by peaking at the NDI band and displaying consistently lower reflectance across most other wavelengths—consistent with the higher absorption typical of chlorophyll-rich canopies. Meanwhile, the Water signature, represented by a blue line with circular markers, maintains low

reflectance throughout the spectrum, aligning with its known optical behaviour of absorbing rather than reflecting light. Moreover, the inclusion of error bars in these spectral plots—derived from the standard deviation between the mean reflectance and its lower bound—provides additional context on the variability and uncertainty inherent in the measurements. For instance, narrow error bars in the Vegetation and Water classes suggest a high degree of homogeneity in their spectral responses, while broader error margins in the sand classes indicate more variability, potentially due to differences in grain size, moisture content, or mixing of new and old sediments.

Feature importance analysis has proven invaluable for enhancing classification accuracy in coastal and other environmental settings. By using methods such as permutation importance [33,74] researchers can systematically evaluate the contribution of each variable—whether derived from spectral or geometric attributes—toward model performance. For example, [75] improved classification accuracy to 85 % by combining conventional Landsat spectral information with shape descriptors of coastlines. This multi-faceted approach helped capture subtle morphological traits that purely spectral data might overlook. Similarly, [33] showed that adding canopy height from GEDI to Sentinel-1/2 observations led to a 93.45 % accuracy, demonstrating how fusing multiple data sources can better characterize diverse environmental conditions.

Fundamentally, feature importance ranks the utility of each input variable—whether it's a specific wavelength from a multispectral sensor or a topographic index—in distinguishing target classes [76,77]. Within a coastal context, different spectral bands may excel at differentiating water from wet sand, while certain geometric features might be more indicative of erosion corridors or dune vegetation. This level of detail informs both algorithm design and data acquisition strategies, ensuring researchers collect—and ultimately emphasize—the data most critical for accurate classification.

In parallel, PCA aids in dimensionality reduction by extracting the most variance-rich components from multi-band or multi-feature datasets [78]. This step not only cuts down on computational overhead but also helps maintain the integrity of essential environmental signals, especially when large numbers of spectral or ancillary bands are present. Integrating DTMs into this PCA-based framework can significantly enrich the analysis by adding a spatial dimension to the spectral data. This 3D perspective is often crucial in coastal mapping, where elevation-dependent ecological processes—like dune formation or marsh inundation—play a central role [79].

Taken together, feature importance assessments, PCA-driven dimensionality reduction, and the inclusion of topographic variables constitute a robust methodological toolkit for coastal studies. These steps enable both high-accuracy land-cover mapping and a clearer understanding of which data inputs drive the most reliable predictions—ultimately guiding more targeted and efficient data collection and modelling efforts in coastal research and beyond, and what we present in our research.

5.4. Application to coastal monitoring

The indicator in this study offered key insights into the monitoring of coastal sediment deposition, which plays a critical role in understanding ecosystem fragmentation, species isolation, and the resulting reduction in genetic diversity – all of which weaken the overall resilience of ecosystems. By examining the movement of sediments and its impact on the marine-terrestrial boundary, the research highlights the necessity of maintaining the integrity of these boundaries to preserve essential ecosystem services, such as nutrient cycling, storm buffering, and biodiversity support.

High-resolution analysis (10 cm) enabled the detection of fine-scale sediment patterns, revealing deposition areas throughout the vegetated zones of coastal wetlands. This level of detail allows for a more nuanced understanding of sediment deposition processes, which are driven by

storm surges and episodic flooding or higher sand influx related to strong winds. Therefore, the findings underscore the importance of high-resolution remote sensing for environmental monitoring and coastal conservation. The detailed knowledge is critical for developing conservation strategies that target vulnerable ecosystems and biodiversity hotspots in coastal areas [80].

The findings further reveal that boundary shifts, caused by sediment transport, not only reshape the physical structure of coastal landscapes but also have significant ecological impacts. As sediments advance inland, they cause wetland ecosystems to fragment, isolating species and reducing the ecosystem's ability to adapt to environmental changes. This fragmentation weakens the adaptive capacity of species and disrupts ecological balance. By stressing the importance of effective management of these boundary zones, the research underscores the need to preserve the integrity of coastal ecosystems to boost their resilience in the face of climate change and other environmental challenges.

6. Conclusions

This study demonstrated the effective application of high-resolution remote sensing combined with rigorous measurement methodologies to enhance the classification and monitoring of coastal environments. By integrating LiDAR, RGB, and multispectral data, we significantly improved the accuracy and detection capabilities for identifying coastal sediment deposits, achieving a spatial resolution of up to 10 cm. This high level of detail provided a comprehensive understanding of sediment movement and landscape alterations resulting from storm surges and extreme weather events.

Through meticulous calibration and validation of both multispectral and LiDAR datasets, we developed a robust classification algorithm optimized for high accuracy and adaptability across coastal sandy barrier environments. The calibration processes adhered to metrological standards, ensuring traceability and reliability of the measurements. By employing the GEE platform and integrating diverse data types within the classification workflow, we achieved a classification accuracy of 90 %. This underscores the effectiveness of our approach in delineating distinct environmental features with high precision and demonstrates the importance of advanced measurement techniques in environmental monitoring.

The application of multispectral imaging to marine coastal flooding deposits showcased its potential for conducting cost-effective and time-efficient surveys aimed at identifying areas impacted by past catastrophic events. The standardized measurement procedures facilitated the detection of storm-induced morphological changes and enabled the recognition of surface sediments potentially deposited during storms or tsunamis. The ability of multispectral cameras to detect traces of such events, which can persist on the coastal surface for years, highlights the importance of precise measurement techniques in environmental reconstruction.

Moreover, the integration of LiDAR and multispectral imaging allowed for the potential identification of older events, offering insights into catastrophic occurrences not recorded in historical archives. This integrated measurement approach enhances our capacity to reconstruct past environmental disturbances, contributing to a deeper understanding of the long-term dynamics of coastal systems. The study's methodologies adhered to international measurement standards, ensuring that the results are both reliable and reproducible.

The urgent need for ongoing monitoring of coastal sediments was highlighted by the dynamic nature of coastal zones, characterized by continuous sedimentary processes and varying degrees of human impact. Effective management and conservation strategies depend on accurate, timely data obtained through precise measurement techniques. The high classification accuracy achieved in this study demonstrates the potential of our methodology to contribute meaningfully to sediment monitoring efforts. By providing stakeholders with reliable information for decision-making, we contribute to nature conservation

management and underscore the critical role of measurement science in environmental stewardship.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

P. Tysiac: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Resources, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **D. Moskaiewicz:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Investigation, Conceptualization. **. Janowski:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary material

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.measurement.2025.117459>.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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